

STUDIES IN THE NEGATIVELY CHARGED COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS OF
VARIOUS FERRIC SALTS. PART I. NEGATIVELY CHARGED MIXED
SOL OF FERRIC OXIDE AND FERRIC VANADATE

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The negatively charged ferric vanadate sols have been prepared and studied for the first time. The paper describes the composition and various other properties of the sols. The glucose-peptised sol has the composition $19\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{Fe}(\text{VO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the glycerine-peptised sol $7\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}(\text{VO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

In some of the previous publications, Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 587, 391; 1930, 7, 367) have referred to their work on ferric molybdate and tungstate jellies. No work seems to have been done on ferric vanadate sols.

It is long known that the addition of mineral acid to a concentrated solution of an alkali or alkaline earth vanadate throws down vanadium pentoxide to a red-brown amorphous hydrous mass, very much similar to hydrous ferric oxide. Biltz (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1098) treated ammonium vanadate with a dilute solution of hydrochloric acid and obtained vanadium pentoxide as a brownish powder which on thorough washing peptised completely in water giving a clear reddish yellow sol. The optical properties of this sol were studied by Freundlich and co-workers (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1915, 7, 207; *Phys. Z.*, 1915, 16, 422; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1916, 22, 27); the nature of the particles was studied by Zoher (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1921, 98, 293; 1923, 105, 119); and Dhar and collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 441; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 1905) studied in details the stability and various other characteristics of dilute as well as concentrated vanadium pentoxide sols and the condition of jelly formation. Though vanadium pentoxide sol has been studied in details, not much attention has been paid to the study of metallic vanadate sols.

In a recent communication, Mushran (*Current Sci.*, 1945, 14, 233) has observed that in presence of glucose, ferric chloride dissolves a considerable amount of ammonium vanadate to give a red coloured sol of ferric vanadate which bears a positive charge. In another communication Mushran (*Current Sci.*, 1945, 14, 123) has shown that if, however, ammonium vanadate is in excess, a permanent precipitate of ferric vanadate is obtained which can be dispersed by caustic soda to give a clear deep red sol of ferric vanadate which bears a negative charge. The peptisation is greatly facilitated by the addition of glucose or glycerine. In this paper we have undertaken the detailed study of the properties and composition of the sol.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Sol (A) was prepared by mixing 50 c.c. of ferric chloride (corresponding to 30.36 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre), 75 c.c. of ammonium vanadate (corresponding to 6.5485 g. of V_2O_5 per litre), 25 c.c. of a 20% glucose solution and 75 c.c. of an *N*-NaOH solution. The total volume was raised to 250 c.c. The sol was dialysed for six days.

Sol (B) was prepared by mixing 26 c.c. of ferric chloride (of the same strength), 40 c.c. of ammonium vanadate (of the same strength), 15 c.c. of glycerine and 40 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution. The total volume was raised to 130 c.c. The sol was dialysed for two days.

Composition of Sols.

The amount of vanadium in the sol was estimated by dissolving the sol in Merck's hydrochloric acid and adding to this a known amount of standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. The excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate was titrated against a standard solution of potassium dichromate using potassium ferricyanide as an external indicator. The method is based on the fact that pentavalent vanadium is reduced quantitatively to the quadrivalent state by ferrous ammonium sulphate. The excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate gives a measure of vanadium pentoxide present. In these titrations, the iron is oxidised before the vanadium. The amount of iron in the sol was estimated by the method of Penny (*Dingl. Polyt. J.*, 149, 490) by reducing ferric iron to the ferrous state by the addition of a freshly prepared stannous chloride solution the excess of which was removed by mercuric chloride and titrating iron against standard potassium dichromate solution. In order to find out how much of the vanadate is in the combined state with iron, a known volume of the sol was coagulated by potassium chloride. The coagulum was collected, thoroughly washed and estimated for vanadate. The coagula have also been obtained cataphoretically and the concordance of the results shows that the equilibrium between the free and combined vanadate is not appreciably altered during these processes. The combined iron corresponding to this amount of vanadate was calculated on the assumption that the ferric vanadate is $\text{Fe}(\text{VO}_3)_3$. The rest of the iron is present as hydrated ferric oxide. From the ratio of the free to the combined iron, the empirical formula of the sol can be suggested.

TABLE I

Per litre	Sol A. Glucose sol.	Sol B. Glycerine sol.
Total Iron	2.9595 g.	2.5686 g.
Total Vanadium (V_2O_5)	1.3741	1.0914
Combined Vanadium (V_2O_5)	0.7276	0.8167
Free Vanadium (V_2O_5)	0.6465	0.2747
Combined Iron	0.1488	0.1669
Free Iron	2.8107	2.4017
Viscosity of sol	0.00825	0.00839
Viscosity of water	0.00803	0.00803
Water, bound	0.01895	0.07898
Empirical formula	$19\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{Fe}(\text{VO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$7\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}(\text{VO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

The amount of bound water per litre of the sol was calculated from the Hatscheck's equation (*Kolloid Z.*, 1911, 8, 34) expressed in the following form :

$$\text{Bound water per litre} = \frac{1000}{A} = 1000 \left(\frac{\eta_s - \eta_w}{\eta_s} \right)^3$$

where A is the ratio of the total volume of water in the sol to the volume of water bound, η_w is the viscosity of water at 30° and η_s is the viscosity of the sol at the same temperature (cf. Prakash, *Kolloid Z.*, 1932, 60, 184). The amount of water, thus computed, is not strictly the water molecularly combined; a part of it is associated with the micelles by the adsorptive forces.

The sols were coagulated cataphoretically and by $N/2$ -KCl, centrifuged and the hydrogen ion concentration of the supernatant layers was determined by Hildebrand's hydrogen electrode. The following p_H values were recorded.

Glucose sol (A), 7.21 (KCl coagulated);
7.33 (cataphoretically coagulated).

Glycerine sol (B), 7.32 (KCl coagulated);
7.48 (cataphoretically coagulated).

Conductivities of Sols.

In the following tables, our observations on the conductivities of these sols at various temperatures, at various dilutions and also the values on ageing are recorded.

TABLE II

Dilutions	Conductivity values at dilutions (30°).		Date.	Conductivity values on ageing (30°).	
	Conductivity			Conductivity	
	Glucose sol (A).	Glycerine sol (B).		Glucose sol (A).	Glycerine sol (B).
Original sol (X)	7.94×10^{-4} mhos.	14.23×10^{-4} mhos.	22.4.45	7.94×10^{-4} mhos.	—
5X/6	6.68	12.10	28.4.45	—	14.23×10^{-4} mhos.
2X/3	5.36	10.16	15.5.45	8.16	—
X/2	4.08	8.21	20.5.45	—	14.46
X/3	2.67	5.90	2.6.45	8.46	—
X/6	1.34	3.11	15.6.45	—	14.98
			2.7.45	8.88	16.52

Conductivity values at diff. temperatures.

Temp.	Glucose sol (A)		Glycerine sol (B)	
	Conductivity.	Diff. per 5° .	Conductivity.	Diff. per 5° .
40°	9.31×10^{-4} mho.	0.69	16.49×10^{-4} mhos.	1.15
35	8.62	0.68	15.34	1.11
30	7.94	0.70	14.23	1.20
25	7.24	0.69	13.03	1.13
20	6.55	0.68	11.90	1.18
15	5.87		10.72	
Temperature of zero conductance (extrapolated)			-23°	-28.5°
Temperature coefficient per 1°			0.136	0.2312

A perusal of the above table shows that in the case of the glucose sol (A), the conductivities are approximately proportional to the dilutions, whilst in the case of the glycerine sol (B), the conductivities at various dilutions are always greater than those computed on the basis of dilution. Marked hydrolysis on dilution of sol (B) is thus indicated. The conductivities of both the sols increase with age. The increased values of conductivities with age indicate that either the adsorbed ions are released on account of loss of surface activity of the colloid particles or ferric vanadate is hydrolysed to give rise to such products which definitely contribute towards conductivity. The hydrolysis of the sols proceeds as follows :—

It was found by Kohlrausch that usually in case of electrolytes the temperature coefficients of conductivities amount to about 2% of the conductivities at 35°. But in case of sols and gels there are certain departures. Prakash (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, **37**, 907) investigated the changes in conductivities of various sols and gels at various temperatures. The temperature coefficient of thorium arsenate jelly investigated by him varied irregularly from 0.9 to 1.4% of the conductance at 35°, whilst in the case of ferric arsenate gel it varied from 1 to 1.4% of the conductance at 35°. The temperature coefficients of conductivity per 1° and the conductances of negatively charged ferric vanadate sols at 35° investigated by us are given below.

	Condy. at 35°	Temp. coeff.
Glucose sol (A) ...	8.62×10^{-4} mhos	0.136
Glycerine sol (B) ...	15.34	0.2312

The temperature coefficient of sol (A) is thus 1.57% of the conductance at 35° and of sol (B) is 1.50% of the conductance at 35°.

Ordinarily it has been found that the conductance of electrolyte solutions becomes zero at temperatures near about 39°. Thorium jellies investigated by Prakash (*loc. cit.*) show that the temperatures of zero conductance range between —15° and 34°. The temperatures of zero conductance for ferric vanadate sols are :—

	Temp. of zero conductance.
Glucose sol (A)	—23°
Glycerine sol (B)	—28.5°

The temperature coefficients and temperatures of zero conductances of sols and gels are different from those of the true electrolytes for the obvious reason that as the temperature is raised, the colloidal micelles also are markedly affected. In some cases, on account of the change in surface energy, they liberate a few of the adsorbed ions which go to contribute towards the conductivities. In the case of the sols of the salts of heavy metals, hydrolysis also takes place to give rise to such products of hydrolysis which too affect electrical conductivities. This accounts for the deviation from Kohlrausch's rule.

Extinction Coefficients of the Sols.

Extinction coefficients were determined by Nutting's spectrophotometer at different dilutions and at different wave-lengths (X stands for the original undiluted sol).

Wave-lengths.	Glucose sol (A)				
	X.	X/2.	X/4.	X/8.	
5000 Å	...	4.16	2.08	1.03	
5200	...	3.28	1.64	0.82	
5400	...	2.28	1.14	0.57	
5600	2.84	1.42	0.71	0.35	
5800	1.94	0.97	0.49	0.24	
6000	1.37	0.67	0.33	0.16	
6200	1.02	0.52	0.26	0.13	
6400	0.76	0.38	0.20	0.10	
6600	0.57	0.28	0.14	0.07	
6800	0.46	0.23	0.12	..	
		Glycerine sol (B)			
5000 Å	4.28	2.46	1.55	0.85	
5200	3.68	1.98	1.18	0.63	
5400	2.85	1.55	0.82	0.42	
5600	1.95	1.05	0.55	0.29	
5800	1.35	0.72	0.39	0.24	
6000	0.95	0.50	0.27	0.16	
6200	0.70	0.37	0.22	0.13	
6400	0.52	0.28	0.20	0.12	

It will be seen from the above table that in the case of sol (A) Beer's law is almost rigidly followed, i.e., the extinction coefficients are almost proportional to the dilutions. In the case of sol (B), the extinction coefficients are always more than those computed on the basis of dilution. The hydrolysis of ferric vanadate at different dilutions has caused deviations in the extinction coefficients—dilution relationship. Our results on the conductivities at different dilutions (Table II) also show similar behaviour.

Coagulation of the Sols.

In the following table are recorded the minimum amounts of electrolytes necessary to coagulate 1 c.c. of the sols in a total volume of 10 c.c., the time allowed in each case being 30 minutes.

TABLE IV

Electrolytes.	Glucose Sol (A)		Glycerine sol (B)	
	Amount necessary to coagulate		Amount necessary to coagulate	
N/2 NaCl	4.6 c.c.		4.0 c.c.	
N/2 KCl	2.8		2.8	
N/2 KNO ₃	2.8		2.8	
N/2 KBr	2.8		2.8	
N/200 Ba(NO ₃) ₂	2.7		2.6	
N/200 Sr(NO ₃) ₂	4.0		3.0	
N/50 AlCl ₃	0.5		0.48	

The coagulating power of the ions thus fall in the following series :—

The effect of dilution on the coagulation values has also been investigated. Total volume was 10 c.c.

TABLE V

Electrolytes.	Glucose sol (A)			Glycerine sol (B)		
	1 c.c. sol.	2 c.c. sol.	3 c.c. sol.	1 c.c. sol.	2 c.c. sol.	3 c.c. sol.
N/2 NaCl	4.6	5.0	5.4	4.0	4.6	5.2
N/2 KCl	2.8	3.1	3.4	2.8	3.5	4.2
N/2 KNO ₃	2.8	3.1	3.4	2.8	3.5	4.2

From Table V it is evident that the sols obey the ordinary Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour with dilution. The dilute sol requires lesser amount of electrolyte to coagulate it in a specified time.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The negatively charged sols of ferric vanadate have been prepared and studied for the first time. The sols were prepared by peptising ferric vanadate with caustic soda in presence of glucose and glycerine. The empirical formula for the glucose sol appears to be $19\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{Fe}(\text{VO}_3) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and of the glycerine sol $7\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}(\text{VO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. It will be seen from the results that the following points are very well characterised.

2. The conductivity of the glucose sol is very approximately proportional to the dilution showing that this particular sol did not undergo much hydrolysis during the process of dilution.

3. The glycerine sol contained comparatively a high content of vanadate. Its conductivity therefore did not decrease in the same proportion as the dilution. The product of conductivity and dilution is not constant. It showed a gradual increase as the dilution progressed.

4. The electrical conductivities of both the glucose and the glycerine sols are linear functions of temperatures. The temperature of zero conductance is -23° in the glucose sol and -28.5° in the case of the glycerine sol.

5. The temperature coefficient of conductivity per 1° for the glucose sol is 1.57% of the conductance at 35° , whilst for the glycerine sol it is 1.50% of the conductance at 35° .

6. The ageing effect as studied by the conductivity values is equally prominent in both the sols. The conductivities increase as the time extends.

7. The extinction coefficients of the glucose sol are approximately proportional to the dilutions, whilst in the glycerine sol the extinction coefficients do not decrease in the same proportion as the dilution.

8. The p_{H} values of the dispersion medium lie between 7.21 and 7.48 showing that the sols are slightly basic owing to the stabilising hydroxide ions.

9. The sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour on dilution.